

Impact of Invasive Species on Guam's Forests: It's Worse Than You Think

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Many people know about the ecological disaster caused by the brown treesnake which killed almost all forest birds on Guam during the last century. Not only did we lose the birds, but also the ecosystem services they provided such as spreading seeds, eating insect pests and pollinating some plants. However, few people are aware of the current ecological disaster. Our forests are rapidly being killed by invasive insects.

In 2002 a US Forest Service survey estimated the total number of trees (with a stem diameter of greater than five inches) in Guam's forests. According to the survey, the three most populous trees were Guam's endemic cycad, fadang (16% of total), coconut palm (12%), and palma brava (11%). These three prominent species, accounting for 39% of all trees in Guam's forests, are being killed at an alarming rate by uncontrolled outbreaks of invasive insects.

Fadang evolved in Micronesia and was perfectly suited for survival on Guam, being resistant to typhoons and drought. This is why it was the most abundant tree on Guam for thousands if not millions of years. That began to change when a tiny insect pest, the Asian cycad scale (ACS), was found on ornamental cycads in Tumon in 2003. ACS lives under a white, waxy scale cover and lives by sucking sap from cycads. Without treatment, cycads become totally covered with scales and start to die within a year. The first plants to die were ornamentals in Tumon, but the infestation quickly spread to wild plants. Surveys indicated that 90% of fadang plants were killed by ACS and other recently arrived invasive insects, resulting in fadang being added to the US endangered species list in 2015. Introduction of a lady beetle which eats ACS is now protecting mature fadang plants, but the remaining plants are not reproducing because all seedlings are still being killed.

Coconut palm, palma brava, formerly the second and third most abundant trees in Guam's forests, are being killed by coconut rhinoceros beetles (CRB), first discovered in Tumon in 2007. Adult beetles damage palms when they bore into crowns to feed on sap. When beetles bore through developing fronds within the crown, this results in distinctive V-shaped cuts when the fronds emerge. Occasionally, CRB adults will kill palms by damaging the meristem or growing tip within the crown. This usually happens only when a palm is attacked by many beetles during an outbreak. Immature CRBs, referred to as grubs, do no damage because they feed only on dead plant material such as green waste and even soil which is high in organic content. The favored feeding site for CRB grubs is a dead, standing coconut.

An attempt was made to eradicate CRB from Guam. But this failed when the beetle spread to all parts of the island by 2010. Many palms with V-shaped cuts were seen throughout Guam, but there was little tree mortality until abundant CRB breeding sites in the form of decaying vegetation were left in the wake of Typhoon Dolphin which passed over the island in 2015. In months following Dolphin, large numbers of CRB adults emerging from these breeding sites began to kill palms. Guam is now in the midst of an uncontrolled, self-sustaining outbreak whereby dead standing coconuts generate large numbers of adults which kill more palms resulting in even more adults. This feedback cycle will not stop until the beetles have exhausted their food supply, resulting in death of most palms on Guam. Entomologists have attempted to stop the outbreak by introducing CRB disease organisms. Unfortunately, a viral disease which provided long-lasting CRB population control when released on many Pacific islands does not work with the Guam population. It turns out that CRB on Guam is a newly discovered virus-resistant biotype of the pest, referred to as CRB-G. This

super beetle is not just a problem on Guam. Coconuts and other palms are being killed by CRB-G in Papua New Guinea, Solomon Islands, Palau, Oahu and Rota. Pacific based entomologists are scrambling to find virus isolates which can be used to control CRB-G.

Only on Guam: the treesnake killed the birds in Guam's forests; now invasive insects are killing the three most abundant tree species in these forests.